

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR)

A View from the Veterinary Residues Committee

Introduction

Most farm animals that fall ill will be treated with an authorised veterinary medicine on the advice of a veterinary surgeon who must prescribe the appropriate medicine. This is important as safe food comes from healthy animals.

The decision to treat an animal with an appropriate available treatment will depend on the severity of the illness, any legal controls relating to the diagnosis and the value of the animal, particularly in terms of maintaining good breeding stock. This is different from human medicine where people must be treated using the different treatment options open to the medical doctors.

However the development of resistance to antibiotics is becoming an issue of increasing concern, impacting on both animal and human health. Consequently the EU is considering restricting or removing some key antibiotics from veterinary use to protect their efficacy in human medicine. There is a need to maintain a balanced view between addressing public concerns over antimicrobial resistance and ensuring a sufficient supply of safe and nutritious food from healthy animals that are free from pain, injury and disease.

The VRC was established as an independent scientific expert group to advise Ministers and the CEOs of the VMD and FSA on residues surveillance programmes. As such, it has a clear role in monitoring the presence of veterinary medicines residues in food. AMR is for others to quantify and to offer advice to the Government, but the VRC hopes this addition to the debate from our perspective will be useful, particularly to the lay person and some of our stakeholders

What is an antibiotic or an antimicrobial? ⁱ

An antibiotic exerts an action against bacterial growth only. Antimicrobials are compounds which exert an action against micro-organisms and exhibit selective toxicity towards them. The term is often used synonymously with antibiotic. It now includes any substance of natural, semi-synthetic or synthetic origin, which inhibits the growth of, or kills, micro-organisms (bacteria, fungi, viruses and protozoa).

The importance of antimicrobial use in animals

Antimicrobial medicines remain essential in the treatment of sick animals affected by this range of micro-organisms. The current range of antimicrobials authorised for use in animals provides a key element in the veterinary surgeon's ability to treat disease. There are two main reasons for this view:

1. Animal Welfare is of increasing concern to consumers. Withholding antimicrobials may compromise an animal's well-being. The need for therapeutic options is likely to remain, despite much progress being made in the development of preventative flock/herd health strategies used in combination by farmers and their vets.

2. Food security and supply is of increasing concern. The ability to produce sufficient food of acceptable quality to feed a growing world population is a huge task. Sustainable livestock farming remains an important global objective. Although preventative strategies for disease are essential, prompt and effective therapeutic options that resolve clinical signs of disease and minimise long term impacts on livestock productivity are vitally important from economic and sustainability perspectives.

Development of antimicrobial resistance

Antimicrobial resistance is defined as the ability of a micro-organism to grow or survive in the presence of an antimicrobial at a concentration that is usually sufficient to inhibit or kill micro-organisms of the same species. Micro-organisms may be tolerant, or inherently resistant to particular antimicrobials, or they may acquire resistance to an antimicrobial to which they are normally sensitive.

Antibiotics act in a variety of ways to control bacterial infections however the relationship between the use of an antibiotic and the subsequent emergence of a resistant bacterium is not fully understood. For the majority of antimicrobials AMR is the result of the acquisition of extrachromosomal resistance genes (DARC/ARHAI 2012).

The use of antibiotics in agriculture has been cited as a major source of antibiotic resistance in pathogenic bacteria of humans. However the scientific data does not seem to indicate such a clear cut relationship. Indeed other factors such as past and present levels of prescription of human medicines, the widespread use of other antimicrobial agents and the increase in our global travel may also have an important role to play. It is too easy to take a simplistic view of animal versus human AMR. In reality a complex pattern of interactions is emerging within an evolving microbial ecology.

Proposed Changes

The European Commission is currently reviewing legislation relating to the use of veterinary medicines and medicated feeding stuffs. As part of the review it is considering the restriction or possible removal of some key antibiotics from veterinary use to protect their efficacy in human medicine. However, the link between on-farm use and the primary development of resistance in human pathogens is unlikely (Reid 2011). Changes must be based on best scientific evidence and ensure that the correct balance is struck between controlling the risk of AMR in animals affecting the treatment of humans and providing the necessary medicines to enable the UK's high standard of animal health and welfare to be maintained.

Antimicrobial Stewardship in the UK

Like all medicines, antimicrobials should be used responsibly which means:-

- Farms should be managed so that the risk of disease developing is minimised. Good animal husbandry is essential to reduce the disease challenge.
- When animals become ill they should be treated in accordance with instructions from the farm's veterinary surgeon and any specific protocol laid down should be followed.
- Antimicrobials should only be used as prescribed by the farm's veterinary surgeon and the full course of treatment should be given.
- Critically important antimicrobials should not be used preventively or as first time treatment unless there is clear scientific justification to do so.
- Guidance set out on product labels should be followed.

In treatment of humans and animals all medicines should be used *as little as possible but as much as necessary*. Reducing dosages or the length of treatment simply to use less is not responsible if initial treatment of an individual animal, or herd/flock does not fully cure the problem and further treatment is needed. Using this strategy could encourage the development of resistance which would compromise animal health and welfare.

The farming industry through RUMA (the Responsible Use of Medicines in Agriculture Alliance) has produced detailed guidelines by farm livestock species to show best practice. These are available free to download at www.ruma.org.uk

The Veterinary Residues Committee considers that:

- A balanced view on use of antimicrobials in animal health is necessary
- Antimicrobial resistance can transfer from animals to humans and vice versa and this can lead to treatment problems. However the current evidence is that a clear majority of human antimicrobial resistance stems from the use of antimicrobials in humans (Wassenaar and Silley, 2008).
- Antimicrobials should only be prescribed and supplied by veterinary surgeons. This helps maintain a viable rural veterinary practice network which is essential for notifiable disease surveillance and control, and for ensuring that farm animal welfare is maintained.
- Critically important antimicrobials (CIA's) for human use should be clearly defined and these definitions apply across all EU Member States. Limitations on the use of CIA's in animals (eg as first time treatments) should be supported by robust scientific evidence and clearly shown on product labels.
- The advice available from regulatory and advisory bodies in the UK and within the EU must be followed. In particular, the Committee urges all parties to contribute to making the guidance of the *Office International des Epizooties (OIE)*ⁱⁱ as effective as possible to ensure antimicrobials are used responsibly in farming in all member countries.
- More training, especially Continuing Professional Development (CPD), should be available to vets and farmers to help ensure the most responsible use antimicrobials and to keep up to date with developments on AMR.

The VRC View

The VRC supports measures to reduce the unnecessary use of antibiotics and promote their prudent therapeutic use in animals used for food. However, when considering the removal of antimicrobial veterinary medicinal products from use, and particularly those considered critically important for human use, regulatory changes must be proportionate, appropriate and based on assessment of risk using the best scientific evidence available.

AMR is a complex and emotive issue which requires significant further consideration in partnership between human and veterinary medicine to achieve a balanced outcome. The VRC supports the One Health Agendaⁱⁱⁱ.

ⁱ The Heads of Medicines Agencies (HMA) have produced a definition of the terms “antibiotic” and “antimicrobial” http://www.hma.eu/fileadmin/dateien/Veterinary_medicines/00-HMA_Vet/02-HMA_Task_Force/03_HMA_vet_TF_AMR/2012_11_HMA_agreed_AB_AM_definitions.pdf

ⁱⁱ The Office International des Epizooties (OIE) has developed standards and guidelines to provide methodologies for OIE Member Countries to appropriately address the risk of the emergence or spread of resistant bacteria that result from the use of antimicrobial agents in food producing animals. <http://www.oie.int/our-scientific-expertise/veterinary-products/antimicrobials/>

ⁱⁱⁱ The Royal Veterinary College describes One Health as a comprehensive approach to health that focuses on:

A. Improving health and well-being through the prevention of risks and the mitigation of effects of crises that originate at the interface between humans, animals and their various environments.

B. Promoting multi (cross) sectoral collaborations and a “whole of society” treatment of health hazards, as a systemic change of perspective in the management of risk.
<http://www.rvc.ac.uk/Research/Groups/OneHealth/WhatsOneHealth.cfm>

Reid, SWJ et al, (2011). *An ecological approach to assessing the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance in animal and human populations.*
<http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/early/2011/11/10/rspb.2011.1975.abstract> [accessed 11/03/13]

Trudy M. Wassenaar and Peter Silley (2008). *Antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic bacteria: lessons learned from host-specific pathogens.* *Animal Health Research Reviews*, 9, pp 177-186.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S1466252308001539> [accessed 15/04/13]

DARC/ARHAI, *ESBLs – A threat to human and animal health? Report by the Joint Working Group of DARC and ARHAI.* http://www.vmd.defra.gov.uk/pdf/ESBL_report.pdf [accessed 11/03/13]